

WEB DESIGN TECHNOLOGIES AS A METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING TOOL FOR FUTURE TEACHERS OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *This article emphasizes the importance of the educational-methodological support for the "Web Design" course in preparing future teachers of informatics and information technology. The primary content and didactic support of the course, including tools like HTML, MS Publisher, and Adobe Dreamweaver, as well as principles of design and website structure development, are discussed. Issues such as the lack of resources in Uzbek language and the use of WYSIWYG editors and their role in the educational process are also highlighted.*

Keywords: *web design, Educational-methodological support, Informatics teachers, HTML, Design principles, WYSIWYG editors, Electronic textbooks, Teaching materials.*

In the training of future teachers of informatics and information technologies, educational and methodological support in specialized disciplines, including Web design, is of particular importance. The main organizers of the educational and methodological support of the discipline include the provision of educational tools, electronic textbooks, educational and methodological, regulatory and legal, educational and programmatic, their popularization in the educational process and generalization of advanced pedagogical experience, etc.

The educational and methodological support of the discipline is understood as the content and structure of the discipline, the creation of educational and methodological documents, educational tools and didactic methods necessary for teaching students the content of the curriculum determined by the SES, as well as the effective use of achievements in this area [1].

The creation of educational and methodological support of the discipline is based on certain rules. Firstly, the set of teaching aids and educational and methodological documents must cover the main content of the curriculum. This means that each topic of the curriculum is provided with the minimum number of educational and methodological documents and teaching aids necessary to study each main issue of the educational content. Secondly, an integrated approach requires the implementation of the specified functions of teaching aids and educational and methodological documents. Thirdly, the complexity of didactic support of the educational process is embodied in all the main stages of the pedagogical process [2].

It is necessary to take on the task of creating and developing educational and methodological support in the preparation of future teachers of informatics and information technologies for the specialty of web design, in order to receive full training within the time and content specified in the curricula.

The content of the subject "Web Design" for future teachers of informatics and information technologies mainly involves the study of WYSIWYG editors such as MS Publisher, Adobe Dreamweaver, MS Office system, HTML language, VB Script script language, as well as the study of forms for interactive HTML pages. The use of such applications is called visual design, students

rarely write program code manually, in this case the program code is automatically generated by the WYSIWYG editor [3,4].

The content of the subject "Web Design", which is considered the main specialty for future teachers of informatics and information technologies, involves the mastery of web technologies. Also, the subject program includes the study of the principles of building the information structure of the site, its logical and physical structure, the basic principles of design, and the study of composition and color theory for decorating a website [5]. The study does not pay attention to such important aspects as the study of technological methods for creating individual elements of web pages and the design of a website as a holistic system that includes interrelated components such as structural-functional, artistic, technological [6].

During the research, a number of problems were encountered in creating educational and methodological support for the discipline of Web design. The main of these problems is the lack of educational resources in Uzbek language for this field. There are many educational literature, various forms of information media and Internet resources for the discipline of Web design, but these resources are not enough for the didactic aspect. When studying the latest literature on the discipline of Web design, there are various types of resources for the development of competence in the field under study among future computer science teachers. Four main sources can be distinguished from their work: Web design reference books, electronic textbooks, scientific articles and forums [7,8].

In materials taken from the Internet, in particular scientific articles, educational literature, the author presents the material in a free-flowing form, makes various comparisons with other events or incidents in his life and the lives of his acquaintances, which in many cases makes it very difficult to perceive the main information that could be very useful [9].

Processing articles in order to identify the main ideas that need to be conveyed to students in the field of web design takes a lot of time, sometimes there are ideas that do not express anything other than the author's personal point of view. Such literature is less suitable for use in the educational process, since it requires significant preliminary processing.

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